

ECONOMICS

MECHANISMS OF ADAPTATION OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES TO THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY: INTERNATIONAL PRACTICES

Abdullina L.

master's degree, Bauman Moscow State Technical University

Abstract

The article examines the mechanisms of adaptation of small and medium enterprises (SME) to the circular economy (CE). It analyzes international practices for integrating circularity principles into business models. The study explores examples of government programs and private initiatives supporting SMEs in Europe and the USA, as well as methods for optimizing resource use and minimizing waste. Economic and social aspects of adaptation, including tax incentives and impacts on employment, are discussed. The research emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive approach for the successful integration of the CE into SME operations.

Keywords: circular economy (CE), small and medium enterprises (SMEs), international practices, sustainable development (SD), government support, optimization, tax incentives.

Introduction

In the context of global environmental and economic challenges, such as climate change, depletion of natural resources, and the need to reduce waste levels, the circular economy (CE) is an essential concept for ensuring sustainable development (SD). Unlike the traditional linear model («take – use – dispose»), it envisions the creation of closed loops where products and materials are reused, recycled, and recovered, minimizing waste and reducing the strain on natural resources. In this model, small and medium-sized enterprises (SME) play a significant role, as they constitute a large part of the global economy.

The aim of this article is to analyze the mechanisms by which SME adapt to the principles of CE. The study examines international practices for implementing CE strategies in business, as well as the social and economic aspects of SME adaptation.

Main part. Analysis of international practices for SME adaptation to the CE

The economic development model aimed at maximizing resource use and minimizing waste through the creation of closed loops is called the CE. The main principles of CE include designing products with future recycling in mind, using renewable resources, and implementing systems that allow materials to be returned to production chains (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Diagram of linear and circular economies

At the international level, the CE is actively developing, and SME serve as successful examples of how businesses can adapt to SD models. In some countries, CE is supported at the government level through incentive programs and legislation, while in others, it evolves through private initiatives and partnerships.

In Europe, the Spanish company **Ecoalf** is a successful example of integrating circular principles into the textile industry. The company recycles plastic collected from the Mediterranean Sea and other waste materials, such as old tires and fishing nets, to produce clothing. According to the latest report, in 2022, Ecoalf recycled 366,68 tons of waste as part of its «Upcycling

the Oceans» project, increasing this figure by 93% compared to the previous year. Additionally, the company saved over 12,26 billion liters of water in the production process of its fall-winter collection, thanks to innovative recycling technologies and reduced water consumption in production processes [1]. Ecoalf's example demonstrates how textile SME can successfully implement circular models while remaining competitive and attracting customers interested in eco-friendly products.

Among American companies, **Thread International** stands out. Recycled plastic is utilized in the production of polyester and other materials, which are then

crafted into backpacks, bags, and clothing. Apart from decreasing waste, the business also generates employment opportunities and enhances the quality of life in regions where waste is gathered. Thread International strives to achieve complete transparency in its supply chain, enabling customers to trace the source of products and observe how their buying choices affect the environment and communities in less developed nations. Since being established in 2011, Thread International has received more than \$9,7 million in funding, allowing the company to grow and solidify its presence in the field of sustainable and renewable materials [2].

Another American company successfully implementing CE practices is **Bamboozy**. The company focuses on making environmentally friendly bamboo items like reusable straws, cutlery, and personal hygiene products. Bamboozy seeks to decrease the adverse effects on the environment through the utilization of sustainable resources. An example is bamboo, which can grow 3-5 feet every week and can be harvested without replanting, making it one of the quickest-growing plants in the world. Bamboozy urges its clients to bring back used items for recycling and repurposing, aiding in the reduction of waste and prolonging the lifespan of products. As per company reports, it is defined as a social enterprise because it focuses on tackling social, cultural, or environmental issues while maintaining financial sustainability.

Mechanisms for supporting SME adaptation to CE principles

There are various approaches aimed at integrating sustainable technologies into business models. In the **European Union (EU)**, support for SME is provided at both national and supranational levels. One of the key tools includes **financial and tax incentives**, such as grants and subsidies for developing and implementing recycling and reuse technologies. For instance, the Horizon Europe program allocates €93,5 billion between 2021 and 2027 for research and innovation in SD [3].

In individual EU countries, tax incentives also support companies implementing eco-friendly technologies, reducing the costs of transitioning to more sustainable production models. For example, in Germany, the Growth Opportunities Act provides a 15% investment premium for companies investing in energy-efficient and climate-neutral technologies. This applies to funding for movable assets and energy management systems, with a maximum subsidized expense of €30 million [4]. Additionally, under the Research Allowance Act, companies can receive a tax credit of up to 35% for R&D-related expenses, with the maximum credit raised to €10 million in 2024 to encourage SME participation in innovation projects.

In **Spain**, the España Circular 2030 law provides several support measures for companies engaged in recycling, reuse, and waste minimization. One key tool is the reduction of the corporate income tax rate to 23% for enterprises with a turnover of less than €1 million [5]. Furthermore, tax credits for research and development and technological innovation are available for companies implementing recycling and reuse projects, with maximum credits reaching 30% of relevant

investment costs, which is particularly beneficial for SME looking to reduce expenses associated with transitioning to sustainable production models.

In the **USA**, SME support for CE is provided at the federal and local government levels [6]. For example, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) runs programs like Sustainable Materials Management, offering grants and technical assistance to SME engaged in recycling and reuse efforts.

The Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) and the Qualifying Advanced Energy Project Tax Credit (48C) offer significant tax incentives to support SME adopting CE principles. For instance, the §48C program provides an investment tax credit of up to 30% of certified project costs aimed at implementing clean technologies and circular business models. These credits apply to SME working in key material recycling sectors such as lithium-ion batteries and rare earth elements, as well as waste management and renewable energy projects.

Additionally, in the USA, Environmental Justice Grants offer tax credits to companies undertaking renewable energy projects in low-income communities, providing up to 20% of total project costs to stimulate SD investments.

Individual states also offer additional tax incentives and subsidies. For instance, the **California** Competes Tax Credit (CalCompetes) program allocated over \$34 million in 2023 to support companies developing sustainable technologies and creating green jobs. This investment led to the creation of approximately 1,500 new jobs and generated significant investments totaling \$2 billion [7].

In **New York**, the Green Jobs-Green New York program offers tax incentives and subsidies for SME implementing energy-efficient technologies and recycling efforts. The state also provides Property Tax Exemptions for solar energy installations and other sustainable systems, allowing businesses to reduce their tax burden when investing in renewable energy.

Another mechanism for supporting SME adaptation includes **training and advisory programs**. In **Europe**, the Erasmus for Young Entrepreneurs program provides opportunities for experience exchange, allowing SME entrepreneurs to learn from successful implementations of circular models in other EU countries. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) offer technical assistance programs and funding for SME, as well as platforms for sharing best practices and research on CE models.

In the **USA**, training programs are also being developed, often in collaboration with universities and private organizations. For example, Small Business Development Centers (SBDC) provide SME with consulting services on SD, including transitioning to circular business models. These centers assist SME in developing strategies for waste minimization, optimizing resource use, and implementing recycling technologies.

Strategies for implementing circular models in SME

A structured strategy is needed for successful adoption of circular models in SME, which involves incorporating new technologies, making organizational

adjustments, and fostering partnerships with different groups involved.

Advances in technology play a crucial role in adjusting to the circular economy. SME can make use of digital technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) to monitor product lifecycles, enhance resource management, and reduce waste. For instance, by installing monitoring and data analysis systems, production processes can be optimized leading to enhanced efficiency and decreased resource usage [8]. Additionally, the use of 3D printing technologies can facilitate localized production and reduce logistics costs, aligning with CE principles.

To successfully transition to the circular economy, SME must rethink their business models by integrating closed-loop principles. One effective strategy is to implement «Product as a Service» (PaaS) models, where instead of selling products, companies provide access to a product or service on a temporary basis. This approach reduces the number of resources produced and consumed, as companies maintain control over their products' lifecycle, ensuring repair, upgrades, and recycling [9]. Another model is reverse logistics, which involves returning used products for further recycling and material reuse.

An essential aspect of CE is optimizing supply chains and resource management. SME can create local and regional partnerships to improve logistics and minimize transportation costs. It is also crucial to establish

systems for the efficient use of secondary materials and waste as resources for production.

Employee training and skills development are important components of implementing circular models. SME can utilize professional development programs and training initiatives offered by public and private organizations to increase workers' awareness of sustainable production and recycling. Upskilling in resource management and sustainable technologies enables businesses to effectively adopt new methods and quickly adapt to changing market conditions.

Successful CE implementation is impossible without active collaboration with partners, government bodies, and international organizations. SME can develop cooperative initiatives and partnerships focused on the shared use of technologies, resources, and knowledge. For example, participation in clusters and consortia allows businesses to pool efforts and share experiences, accelerating innovation and the development of circular practices. Collaboration with large companies can also be beneficial for integrating SME into sustainable supply chains and gaining access to new markets and technologies.

Social and economic aspects of SME adaptation

Adapting SME to modern CE requirements requires a comprehensive approach that encompasses various features. Implementing sustainable business models not only helps reduce environmental impact but also improves companies' market positions (table 1).

Table 1.

Social and economic aspects of SME Adaptation to the CE

Aspect	Description	Impact
Change in consumer preferences and demand	The growing interest in eco-friendly and sustainable production requires SME to adapt their business models and shift towards circular practices.	Increasing demand for eco-friendly products encourages businesses to invest in recycling and sustainable technologies, strengthening their market positions.
Impact on employment and development of local communities	CE creates jobs in waste recycling, logistics, and implementation of ecological solutions, improving the social and economic conditions of local communities.	The growth in employment and skill development in new sectors contributes to the SD of regions and reduces unemployment rates.
Economic sustainability and competitiveness of SME	Implementing circular models reduces costs for raw materials and optimizes resource use, enhancing profitability while increasing resilience to market fluctuations.	Using recyclable materials and optimizing resource management can improve profitability and make SME more competitive in the face of economic and market changes.

The adaptation of SME to the CE has a complex impact on the social and economic environment, leading to significant changes in market structure and regional development. One of the key findings is that SME adaptation requires the integration of innovative technologies and a new approach to resource management, which involves considerable costs and the need for access to investments. This, in turn, creates a demand for governmental and international support, including tax incentives and educational programs, to enable SME to effectively implement circular models.

Another important aspect is the changing role of SME in the economy. CE-oriented enterprises become crucial participants in local and global supply chains, and their contribution to economic development and

employment increases. The development of new economic sectors, such as recycling, creates conditions for job creation and stimulates the growth of skilled labor, which strengthens the socio-economic resilience of regions.

Moreover, CE promotes the diversification of SME activities and enhances their resilience to market fluctuations. The transition to the use of recycled materials and the development of products with a long lifecycle enable organizations to reduce dependence on raw material price fluctuations, thereby increasing their competitiveness and adaptability to economic challenges. As a result, integrating CE principles becomes not just a strategic choice but a necessary condition for SME growth in modern conditions.

Conclusion

Due to their flexibility and ability to adapt to changes, SME play a crucial role in the transition to a CE, making them essential participants in this process. International practices indicate that successful SME adaptation to CE principles requires a comprehensive approach that includes the implementation of innovative technologies, the development of partnerships, and securing government support. Incentive systems, such as tax breaks and subsidies for the development of recycling and reuse technologies, have proven effective in the EU and the USA. Furthermore, collaboration with large companies, integration into sustainable supply chains, and participation in educational and advisory programs are essential elements for enhancing SME competitiveness within the CE framework. The adoption of CE principles not only improves environmental performance but also enhances the resilience and economic efficiency of SME, creating new opportunities for growth and development in a globalized world.

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